

THE ROLE OF ECONOMIC THEORY IN THE DEVELOPING TIME AND SIGNIFICANCE

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Abstract. *This article provides information about the role of economic theory in the life of people today, that is, in the life of society. In addition, economic theory can provide knowledge that helps a person to adapt to the modern economic system of society and to understand himself.*

Key words: *economy, production, need, capital, material demand, labor market.*

Аннотация. *В данной статье представлена информация о роли экономической теории в жизни людей сегодня, то есть в жизни общества. Кроме того, экономическая теория может дать знания, помогающие человеку приспособиться к современной экономической системе общества и разобраться в себе.*

Ключевые слова: *экономика, производство, потребность, капитал, материальный спрос, рынок труда.*

INTRODUCTION

Each person faces various economic problems every day: how to meet the needs of food, housing, clothing, education, recreation, etc., what kind of economic activity to engage in, one or the other whether or not to buy something, whether there is enough income to buy a certain product or provide a necessary service, etc. Thus, the economy becomes an integral part of modern society. To create a strong and prosperous country that can take its rightful place in the modern world, it is necessary to develop a competitive and socially oriented market economy based on science and innovation. We are living in the era of scientific and technical progress,

in the era that determines the economic growth of society with the emergence of new material and spiritual goods and their exchange. Many critics of the modern economy argue that increased economic growth leads to imbalances in the ecological balance and increased unemployment, as professional skills and experience can become obsolete with technological progress. But scientific and technical progress is not only one of the factors of increasing economic growth, but also the main indicator of the development of the whole society. Thus, without new technologies, society will face deep stagnation, which will have very negative consequences for people. A science such as economic theory deals with the study of laws and factors of economic growth.

Economic theory is all theoretical ideas about economic processes and events, economic activity, economic relations, based on logic, historical experience on the one hand, and on theoretical concepts, views, on the other hand. Economists. Economic theory as a science considers the individual as a member of the society, subject to the traditions, nationality, inclinations and political views of the people. Let us see what role economic theory plays for modern society. Everyone knows that a person cannot exist as a part of society without satisfying needs. Tools suitable for needs are called preferences. Profit is something that contains a certain positive meaning - these are products and services, which are tangible and intangible means of satisfying human needs.

RESEARCH METHOD AND METHODOLOGY

The benefits are many. But conditionally they can be divided into two groups - free and economic benefits. Goods that are available in more or less unlimited quantities are free goods (air, solar heat, water in some regions of the earth). Other goods are available in limited quantities and are called economic goods such as bread, CDs, cars, knowledge, programmer services. Economic benefits are goods that can be created only in the economy, as a result of economic creative activity, through production. It is an indisputable fact that production is a necessary factor in

human life. But there are many opinions about what motivates people to engage in activities such as manufacturing. For example, according to psychologists, creativity, relying on imagination, fantasy, intuition, encourages a person to produce material or immaterial benefits.

Others believe that man simply cannot produce anything. After all, the natural state of a person is a state of activity. During your lifetime, you will be engaged in various activities, including manufacturing. There are people who see the whole meaning of production as a necessity only because of physiological needs. All of these points of view have the right to exist and, moreover, they are interrelated, so they should be studied comprehensively. Thus, there should be a single scientific theory that can combine all the obtained results, study the dependence of production on various conditions and develop a strategy for improving the standard of living of society. Such a theory is simply an economic theory, which is not interested in the separate or individual life of this or that person, but in the collective behavior of all people, and moreover, in the system of social production relations.

Economic theory is the main basis of economics.

The interaction of theory and practice is a fundamental principle of economics. Due to theoretically rational thinking, the laws and regulations of economic development are studied together. It is no exaggeration to say that it allows you to make effective decisions on the choice of directions for the use of material resources, and also shows the rational use of resources. In addition, economic theory simply expands a person's worldview, answers many questions relevant to modern society, develops economic thinking, helps to achieve success in business, thereby increasing human well-being. Whether we like it or not, we are now living in the era of market economy, the era of capitalism. And capitalism is a system of domination and subjugation. A system where severe exploitation of wage workers is the accepted norm.

Capital rules everything (translated from Latin kapitalis - boss). If you have no capital, you are a wage worker. Perhaps the whole life will have to work for the "uncle" of the capitalist. Economic theory, taking into account the knowledge of sociology, psychology, history and many other disciplines, is an information supply that allows us to understand how the economic system works. People know how to behave in this system. How to cope, live or thrive in this economic system. Economy can exist and develop only where society exists. Where there is society, there is politics. Economics cannot be outside of politics. Its effectiveness will depend on its level of politicization. It is economic theory that is the basis for the development of an optimal economic policy of the state, the main purpose of which is to eliminate difficulties, as well as to control undesirable processes in the country. In addition, economic theory is primarily a social science that provides fundamental knowledge to all professional economic disciplines: management, finance, credit, accounting, and others. It provides valuable knowledge about the behavior of people in the social environment, helps to make rational decisions.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it can be said that many people ask, if I am not an economist and I do not want to connect my life with economics, why should I know economic theory, it has nothing to do with me. The answer to this question is very simple. No matter what profession a person chooses, no matter what country he chooses for his home, he always remains a part of a single system called society. In order to somehow survive, he must know: what is money; what makes up the price and why it goes up or down, why wages are needed, etc. Every day we have to deal with concepts like tax, profit, banking, credit, rent, income, etc. Without the necessary knowledge, a person cannot live in the modern world. Those who know how the social system works simply "crush" it. Today, more than ever, the phrase is becoming more relevant - "He who has information owns the world." It is the

economic theory that can give a person the knowledge that will help him to adapt to the modern economic system of society and to understand himself.

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